

Fixation of P_2O_5 by Soils in Aqueous Media in Presence of Sodium Salts

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The addition of three different sodium salts viz., sodium chloride, sodium nitrate and sodium sulphate to five typical Indian soils increased, in general, the phosphate fixation. The extent of phosphate fixation is, however, dependent upon the type of soil used and the nature of treatments (treatments A, B and C) given to these soils. The maximum phosphate fixation has been obtained generally with treatment A (high initial soil moisture) by the addition of sodium sulphate in alluvial and alkali soils. This is followed by the additions of sodium nitrate and sodium chloride with treatment A in same soils. Texture of the soil does not appear to influence much on the fixation of phosphate by soils in presence of different sodium salts. Increase in pH by the addition of sodium salts generally favours increased phosphate fixation by soils under all the three different treatments.

THE saturation of soils by sodium is an important phenomenon in relation to soil productivity. It may be a matter of interest to observe whether the addition of sodium salts stimulates the soil to absorb more phosphate or not. The present study has, therefore been carried out with five typical Indian soils viz., black cotton, laterite, alluvial, red and alkali soils in aqueous media under three sets of treatments and with one concentration (i.e., 0.4%) of sodium salt. Since with 0.4% sodium salt, maximum fixation of P_2O_5 by soils occurred, only results obtained under this experimental condition have been reported and discussed here.

Experimental

Five typical Indian soils (viz., Black cotton, Krishna Distt., A.P.; Laterite from Coimbatore, Madras; Alluvial from Naini, Allahabad; Red from Ranchi, Bihar and Alkali soils from Soraon, Allahabad) were collected from a depth of 0-15 cm. These soils were then dried, pulverized and finally passed through 100-mesh sieve. These were then analysed for their different physico-chemical properties (Table 1) by the reported methods¹.

For observing the effects of different sodium salts on phosphate fixation, three different moisture treatments were given to each soil sample.

Treatment A: 10 g. of each experimental soil was taken in glass dishes and treated with 0.4% of each of the sodium salts (sodium chloride, sodium nitrate and sodium sulphate) and also with sufficient but measured amount of water (10 ml) so that the whole experimental plates become oversaturated with it. The experimental plates were allowed to stand one month for reaction.

Treatment B: 10 g. of each soil was taken in glass dishes and subjected for treatment with the same concentrations of the sodium salts used in treatment A. Sufficient but measured amount of water (5 ml.)

was added to just submerge the soil and this was allowed to remain in that condition for a month.

TABLE 1. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS

Constituent	Soils				
	Black cotton % (1)	Late-rite % (2)	Allu- vial % (3)	Red % (4)	Alkali % (5)
HCl-insoluble	66.18	84.75	86.68	72.33	86.97
Total P_2O_5	21.83	9.47	8.58	16.95	7.15
Total Fe_2O_3	9.44	4.08	3.48	6.56	2.60
Total Al_2O_3	12.15	5.32	4.90	10.32	4.46
Total CaO	1.61	0.46	0.26	0.50	0.63
Total P_2O_5	0.25	0.07	0.20	0.08	0.09
Total Na_2O	0.48	0.53	0.45	0.33	1.12
Total N	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.05
Total C	0.95	0.77	0.54	0.88	0.32
C $\neq$ N Ratio	19.00	11.17	6.75	14.37	6.40
Exchange properties m.e./100 g. soil					
Total C.E.C.	32.17	19.56	16.95	23.47	13.48
Total E.C.	29.66	33.33	13.36	16.42	9.10
Ex. Na^+	0.65	2.52	0.63	0.63	7.30
pH	7.50	8.10	7.50	5.30	10.40
Texture	Clay	Sandy loam	Loamy sand	Sandy clay loam	Sandy loam

Treatment C: 10 g. each soil was taken in glass dishes and then treatment with the same sodium salts in concentration as mentioned in treatments A and B. To this, water (2.5 ml) was added periodically to keep it just moist and allowed to stand for a month for reaction.

After the lapse of the experimental period, the soils were dried, pulverised in an agate mortar and kept in oil paper bags. 5 g. of this treated soil was taken in a 100 ml. volumetric flask and a required volume of 0.05 g. P_2O_5 in the form of phosphoric acid was added in it. The volume in each case was made up to the mark with distilled water. The contents were then mixed and allowed to stand for 24 hr. Next day, 5 ml. of the supernatant liquid was taken and analysed for P_2O_5 colorimetrically² using 660 m μ red filter.

The pH values were measured³ by Leeds Northrup pH meter operated on 220V and 50 a/c mains. The initial pH values were taken just after the addition

of sodium salts whereas the final pH values were taken after the incubation period.

All the experiments were carried out in aqueous medium at 30° temperature.

The difference in concentration between the P_2O_5 added to the fixation system and the P_2O_5 present in the system after the experiment, was taken as the amount of P_2O_5 fixed by soils at different conditions.

The values given in Tables 2 to 4 indicate the difference of values between those obtained in presence of the treatments and controls.

TABLE 2. FIXATION OF P_2O_5 BY SOILS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF SODIUM CHLORIDE AT 30°

mg. of P_2O_5 added/5 g. soil = 50 mg.

Soil	mg P_2O_5 fixed 15 g soil			Initial pH			Final pH		
	Treatment			Treatment			Treatment		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
1	11.0	3.0	-1.0	5.6	6.6	6.6	5.9	6.8	6.5
2	-4.0	6.0	0.0	4.8	6.0	5.8	4.7	6.3	5.8
3	12.0	4.0	-3.0	5.0	5.2	5.1	5.3	5.4	5.0
4	0.0	3.0	-2.0	4.6	4.8	5.2	4.6	4.9	5.1
5	7.0	3.0	0.0	6.0	7.0	7.0	6.3	7.2	7.0

TABLE 3. FIXATION OF P_2O_5 BY SOILS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF SODIUM NITRATE AT 30°.

mg. of P_2O_5 added/5 g. soil = 50 mg.

Soil	mg P_2O_5 fixed 15 g soil			Initial pH			Final pH		
	Treatment			Treatment			Treatment		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
1	4.0	3.0	19.0	5.6	6.6	6.6	5.7	6.8	6.8
2	8.0	2.0	21.0	4.8	6.0	5.8	5.2	6.1	6.1
3	20.0	0.0	5.0	5.0	5.2	5.1	5.8	5.2	5.3
4	0.0	-9.0	2.0	4.6	4.8	5.2	4.6	4.5	5.3
5	10.0	2.0	14.0	6.0	7.0	7.0	6.2	7.1	7.3

TABLE 4. FIXATION OF P_2O_5 BY SOILS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF SODIUM SULPHATE AT 30°.

mg. of P_2O_5 added/5 g. soil = 50 mg.

Soil	mg P_2O_5 fixed 15 g soil			Initial pH			Final pH		
	Treatment			Treatment			Treatment		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
1	22.0	3.0	4.0	5.6	6.6	6.6	6.2	6.8	6.6
2	2.0	13.0	-6.0	4.8	6.0	5.8	4.9	6.4	6.1
3	24.0	16.0	0.0	5.0	5.2	5.1	6.0	5.6	5.2
4	16.0	2.0	2.0	4.6	4.8	5.2	5.0	4.9	5.4
5	32.0	6.0	1.0	6.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.2	7.1

Note : 1 = Black cotton soil; 2 = Laterite soil; 3 = Alluvial soil; 4 = Red soil; 5 = Alkali soil.

Results and Discussion

In Tables 2 to 4 it may be observed that the extent of increased phosphate fixation due to the presence of sodium salts is dependent not only on the type of the soil but also on the nature of treatments given to these soil samples. Generally, alluvial soil with sodium nitrate or sodium sulphate and black cotton soil with sodium chloride may be observed to record the maximum phosphate fixation in presence of these salts. In treatment B, alkali soil with sodium nitrate, red soil with sodium chloride and alluvial soil with sodium sulphate recorded maximum phosphate fixation. In treatment C, sodium nitrate in laterite, sodium chloride in alkali soil and sodium sulphate in alluvial soil induced maximum phosphate fixation. Red soils generally do not appear to be much responsive in exhibiting enhanced phosphate fixation in the presence of different sodium salts. Sodium sulphate, in general, induced maximum phosphate fixation in all the five soils with treatment A (high initial soil moisture). However, the efficiency order of treatments recording maximum phosphate fixation is found to be as follows :

$$A > B > C$$

In other words, when the phosphate solution was added along with the sodium salts in presence of high moisture (treatment, A), soils of lower pH became more responsive in relation to enhanced phosphate fixation. Further, in presence of limited soil moisture (treatments B and C) supply, the soils of higher alkalinity especially with sodium nitrate and sodium chloride salts became more efficient in this respect. Since, red soil is acidic, its responsiveness in this matter will only be exhibited as appears in Tables 2 and 3. in presence of sodium chloride and when it is subjected to treatment B.

It may be observed in Tables 2 to 4 that except in sodium nitrate-treated soils of black cotton and laterite, and in sodium chloride treated red soils, generally maximum fixation of phosphate occurred when phosphate solution was added along with the sodium salts and in presence of very high moisture. This favours for a better ionization and consequently for base exchange process between the cations of the electrolytes added and the cations in the lattices of the clay minerals present in the soil clay colloids⁴. It was generally observed that, sodium chloride and sodium nitrate salts took the last positions in soils given treatment A and B respectively. Sodium

nitrate, however, proved more effective in increasing phosphate fixation when the phosphate solution was added at a much later time than the addition of sodium salts and under limited soil moisture supply (treatment C).

De and Sharma⁴ explained, however, that increased phosphate fixation in presence of ammonium salts by Indian montmorillonites will depend on the ratio of $H_2PO_4^-/HPO_4^{2-}$ produced in the adsorption system from H_3PO_4 , similarly phosphoric acid in presence of different sodium salts would produce different quantities of $H_2PO_4^-$ and HPO_4^{2-} ions depending on the type of soil and the nature of treatment given to them. The $H_2PO_4^-$ or HPO_4^{2-} ions so formed would be exchanged with the OH^- ions present in the lattices of the clay minerals of the soil colloids or in soil humus⁶ and the OH^- ions thus liberated would neutralize the acid present in the system. Thus there would be enhancement of the resultant pH (Tables 2 to 4). Further, there might be chances that due to continued association of the soil colloids with the Na^+ ions of the Na-salts and H^+ ions of the added phosphoric acid, there would be shifting primarily of aluminium from lattice to the exchange positions⁷⁻¹⁰ leading to phosphate fixation in different amounts due to surface precipitation of aluminium phosphate. It may be stated here that in both types of phosphate fixation in presence of sodium salts, the extent of fixation would obviously depend on the type of soil and the nature of treatments given to them. These appear to be the probable reasons for the general observation on enhanced phosphate fixation (Tables 2 to 4) by the five Indian soils used in presence of different sodium salts and under high or limited moisture supply (treatments A, B and C).

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